

AGE-RELATED CHARACTERISTICS OF NERVOUS SYSTEM AND HIGHER NERVOUS ACTIVITY

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Annotation: Age-related characteristics of the nervous system and family nervous activity are fully described in this article

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The nervous system, on the one hand, adjusts the metabolic and physiological processes that pass to various tissues, organs and systems, and on the other hand, with the help of it, performs the function of maintaining the connection between the whole organism and the external environment. During ontogeny, various parts of the nervous system unite into a functional system, mature and harmonize with age. During early childhood, the central nervous system develops very rapidly. According to I. P. Pavlov, the characteristic of higher nervous activity is the synthesis of heredity, factors and educational conditions. 50% of a person's general mental development begins to form at the age of four. 1/3 at the age of 4-8, the remaining 20% at the age of 8-17. Therefore, the impact of unpleasant factors in early childhood causes serious disorders of the central nervous system. The impact of unpleasant factors can lead to a strong stimulation of the cerebral cortex. After a short-term excitation, its diffuse inhibition appears. The function of the higher layers of the central nervous system is closely related to the activity of receptors, which are considered peripheral self-receiving mechanisms. Interoreceptors transmit tickling from the internal organs to the cerebral cortex; and exteroceptors provide tickling through the external environment. Sensory analyzers can be considered as exteroceptors (for example, vestibular apparatus, skin, taste, sight, smell, hearing receptors). Each analyzer is 1) peripheral; 2) transferor; 3) it is divided into central parts. Sensory organs are peripheral parts (receptors) that receive external influences and transmit them to the central part - the large hemisphere of the brain.

The cerebral cortex receives sensory stimuli, analyzes and synthesizes them. It is clear from this that the cells of the cerebral cortex of the large hemisphere must be perfectly matured. Due to the insufficient development of the child's nervous system, the cells of the cerebral cortex, the receptive stimulus is functionally insufficient. Due to the insufficient development of the child's nervous system, the cells of the cerebral cortex, the receptive stimulus is functional not enough. When the child is related to the environment, he should closely interact with the environment. This balancing is carried out through a number of mechanisms, such as extero-interoreceptors, humoral regulatory systems, then changes in the function of organs and the adaptive-trophic function of the symptomatic sympathetic system. All these mechanisms are controlled by the cerebral cortex. The complex behavior of a person and the development of higher nervous activity are completely related to the brain and partly to its large hemisphere. From the above, it is known that the nervous system of a newborn child is first of all subject to the high demands of the external environment in order to balance its organism. Such a continuous rise of the cerebral cortex of a newborn child, which is not yet functionally fully developed, puts it in a state of inhibition for a long time, as a result of which the child appears to be in a state of almost constant sleepiness. Anatomical-physiological features of the nervous system of a child differ in that the nervous system of newborns and young children is not sufficiently developed and not divided into classes compared to other systems.

During the first period of the brain's life in the mother's womb (up to the first month), the cerebral cortex is not divided into layers, there are no nerve fibers with a myelin sheath, and at the end of the period in the womb, seven layers of neurons are formed in the cerebral cortex, which are located on top of each other. Although almost all the cerebral folds and furrows are present in the large hemisphere of the newborn child's brain, they are very weakly developed; The structure of the layers of the cerebral cortex is mostly completed only at the end of the period in the womb, but the division of all nerve cells into layers occurs mainly in the postembryonic period (Fig. 5).

At the same time, the structures of the spinal cord, the visual cortex (thalamus opticus), on the contrary, are somewhat improved. The shape of the cerebellum is elongated, and its edges are not clearly visible. Only in the first half of the year, the child's brain macroscopically approaches the brain of an adult. The weight of the brain increases rapidly after birth, the weight of the brain of a newborn child is 360-370 grams, that of a 6-month-old child is 600 grams, and

at the end of the year it is about 900 grams. The weight of the brain of a newborn child is $\frac{1}{8}$ of the weight of the body, and 10 of the weight of an adult. Brain weight doubles at 9 months of age, triples between 1 and 3 years of age, and increases 4-5 times at 20 years of age. The division of brain tissue into layers, that is, the development of nerve tissue, ganglion cells, and nerve fibers proceeds rather slowly. Because in a newborn child, the stratum corneum is divided into few layers and the center of the cortex is not sufficiently developed. The development of the cerebral cortex is especially intense in the first three months after birth. The lack of short branches of dendrites (nerve cells) in nerve cells is very characteristic. The division of nerve cells into layers is mostly completed by the age of 3. At the age of 8, it completely improves (Fig. 6). From the moment of birth, the conducting path is sufficiently developed. The pyramidal tracts are surrounded by myelin membrane in 5-6 months.

Spinal cord. After the birth of the child, the weight of the spinal cord is 2-6 g, and in the future it will grow somewhat slower than the weight of the brain. The growth of the spinal cord goes hand in hand with the development of motor functions; it increases its weight by three ranks at the age of 5, but its difference from the brain is that from the second year its structure approaches the structure of adults. Depending on age, the number of motor cells of the anterior horn increases.

During puberty, the spinal cord increases 4-5 times. When performing a spinal puncture, it should be noted that the lower part of the spinal cord in a newborn child is located at the level of the III lumbar vertebra, and at the age of 4, it is located between the I and II lumbar vertebra, as in an adult. Cranial nerves are surrounded by myelin membrane for up to 3 months, and peripheral nerves for up to 3 years. The vegetative nervous system is active from birth. Thus, the morphological features of the nervous system in early childhood are expressed by the insufficient development of the cerebral cortex, the insufficient separation of nerve cells into layers, and the insufficient wrapping of nerve fibers in the myelin sheath. Accordingly, there are a number of features of the nervous system function in childhood. In the embryonic period, tickling from any point in the first half of pregnancy produces a diffuse reaction of the nervous system, and the tendency to this diffuse reaction is preserved in newborn children. In the second half of pregnancy, it has been determined that exposure is manifested in a certain place. Since the cerebral cortex, pyramidal tracts and striatal body are not fully developed at birth, the entire vital function of the newborn child is regulated mainly by the thalamopallid, that is, the subcortical

system. . For example, the pallidum regulates motor movement; It also depends on the slow, involuntary movements of the fingers and toes, characteristic of a newborn child.

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